

Undoped and Mg²⁺-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles for DSSCs activity

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Investigates the influence of Mg²⁺-doping on the dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) behaviour of anatase TiO₂ nanoparticles. The undoped and Mg²⁺-doped (1,3,5, and 7 at.%) TiO₂ nanoparticles are synthesized by sol-gel method. The effects of Mg²⁺-doping on the structural and optical response of the prepared samples are investigated. XRD measurements are carried out to understand the structural properties of the synthesized samples. Transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM), and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns are used to study their morphologies, particles size, crystallinity and lattice arrangements. The magnetic result demonstrated the prepared Mg²⁺-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles exhibit room temperature paramagnetism. PL was carried out to study the defects in the samples. The presence of defect and their impact on the performance of DSSCs are demonstrated from the PL studies. Further, the current-voltage (I-V) measurements are done for the DSSCs fabricated from the synthesized photoanodes.